

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' ATTITUDES TO NATIONAL AND GENERAL HUMAN VALUES

Sadaddinov U.U.

Researcher at Tashkent state pedagogical university

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Abstract. *The article describes the importance of teacher's hard work in implementing the ideas of developing attitudes towards national and universal values in schools and making students intellectually and intellectually mature.*

Keywords: *student, teacher, national and universal values, teaching process, knowledge, skills, competence, pedagogy, philosophy, psychology, professional activity.*

In raising the spirituality of our people, our national traditions and exemplary values such as kindness embodied in their core, glorifying people, valuing a peaceful and peaceful life, friendship and harmony, and solving various problems together are becoming more and more important. .

These values are instilled in the minds of the young generation on the basis of education. Spiritual and universal values in the pedagogical activity of teachers and educators working in higher educational institutions of our country show how wide their spiritual world is. Attention to universal and spiritual values was in the main place in the views of our great scholars on education. Since ancient times, our forefathers considered knowledge, education and upbringing to be the most important condition and guarantee of human perfection and development of the nation. Human morals reach spiritual maturity only when their behavior and actions are based on the study of science and enlightenment. According to scholars, the realization of humanitarian ideals depends on achieving spiritual perfection, being educated and enlightened. That is why they glorified science as a universal value, called all members of the society to acquire knowledge, appreciated the hard work of teachers [6].

In his works, Abu Rayhan Beruni emphasizes that knowledge is the key to learning national and universal values. An enlightened person is a fighter for the fate of society, the fate of people, and is far from all evil. "The benefit of science is not to collect gold and silver greedily, but to acquire things necessary for a person through it," writes the scholar [2].

In the philosophical interpretation, national and universal values are a set of circumstances that have positive significance for a perfect person, such as freedom, peace, social equality, truth, enlightenment, beauty, goodness, which are of incomparable importance for man and humanity.

The essence of all national and universal human values is the highest feeling - humanity. Philanthropy is a product of a person's honor, conscience and faith. Philanthropy is benevolence, caring, the feeling of striving for material and spiritual support, showing kindness within the framework of faith and conscience. In the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" it is interpreted as one of the main principles of the state policy that "the education of young people is humane and democratic in nature" [1]. In implementing these honorable ideas and making students educated and intellectually mature, first of all, the intense work of the teacher is important. Today, in our country, the issue of bringing up a mature generation to adulthood is recognized as an urgent task. It is of particular importance that our children are not only physically, but also morally and spiritually mature. Therefore, the teacher should have a well-developed sense of the highest

universal values. This feeling should always be reflected in the edges of his perfectly formed pedagogical skills. As a human child acquires knowledge from his youth to the end of his life and strives for intellectual perfection, he achieves all spiritual and universal values thanks to knowledge. A teacher is the main responsible person who promotes science to the people and engages in regular creativity that finds its way into the hearts of young people. The basis of the teacher's creative abilities should be the essence of universal and spiritual values and should be carried out with the feelings of knowledge, guidance, love, patience, contentment, and fatherly tolerance [4].

Thanks to the teacher's hard work in educational activities, students' national and universal values improve over the years. As a result of this hard work, the student should learn national and universal values and grow up to the level of perfection, for this, national and universal values should rise, and a person should become a spiritual person in a broad sense. A well-rounded student who is the result of a teacher's work creates and develops high spirituality in the future, preserves universal values and carefully conveys them to the next generation. The teacher's knowledge, pedagogical skills, and hard work are aimed at educating students and developing their spiritual consciousness based on initiative, activity, business, creativity, and entrepreneurship. Global changes in society, technical and technological progress, changes and innovations in secular sciences require creativity from students. And creativity is a form of activity that takes place only at the expense of intense learning, assimilating national and universal values from students.

Students:

- conscious awareness of the essence of national and universal values as a creative attitude;
- conscientiously feel that in the future, with their honest work, they will affect the social and economic, material and spiritual development of society;
- being able to be proud of the richness of one's spiritual values and its results;
- he should always feel his responsibility to the society by getting education in higher education institutions and becoming a potential professional in the future.

In our country, "the training and education of personnel is carried out on the basis of the principles of national revival and achievements of independence, the rich national, spiritual and intellectual potential of the people, and the content of humanistic education based on universal values" [3]. Particular attention is paid to the personality of the student, to strengthening his passion for education and knowledge, independent work, and the formation of a sense of universal human dignity based on national and universal values.

In the course of our research, we asked teachers about what national and universal values students can learn during their student years: "What national and universal values would you personally advise students during the lesson?" The main content of "Advices" is unclear, the individuality of the pedagogue and the intuition of quick topic selection are not felt in them. During the training, the teacher always gives the same advice. They can be described as follows:

- reminding of the need to study diligently;
- encourage to be spiritual, call to conscientiousness;
- a reminder of the need to develop as a well-rounded person;
- call not to lose humanity.

These calls and exhortations indicate the lack of experience of pedagogues in promoting national and universal values in modern educational institutions and make them think about these

problems. Teachers' answers do not have to be declarative or suggestive, too abstract and impressive.

The teacher's orientation of students to national and universal values in the pedagogical process has also been extensively studied by the scientist. He emphasizes that the following issues are important for the improvement of national and universal values in students:

1) The teacher's ability to promote national and universal values specific to society for students to master.

2) The teacher's desire and ability to effectively promote universal and spiritual values in students during educational processes.

3) The teacher created the necessary conditions for regular acceptance of the promoted national and universal values by students [5].

A.G.Zdravomislov and V.A.Yadov define human orientation to universal values as a person's habituation (or adaptation) to the values based on the material and spiritual culture of society [8].

National and universal values can become an ideal by the subject. In this case, this value becomes a target value capable of influencing the establishment of a person's life position and becoming important.

Values that are not directed to a specific goal can act as a manager of the individual's activity, in which it appears in the mind of the individual as instrumental values that "have to be obeyed to achieve their goals".

National and universal values based on a certain goal can face conflicts if they have opposite directions. Objective values are more stable than instrumental values, but instrumental values are more individualized.

Ideal values reflect the priority of life values known to the student.

Instrumental values reflect the priority of certain types of behavior that lead to the realization of relevant ideal values. Currently, the method of diagnosing spiritual values proposed by the researcher M.Rokich is widespread.

Many scientists consider ideal values as the content of students' educational activities, they are pedagogical values, and among them, they often recognize the following: private prestige; high level of spiritual maturity; creativity; to actively learn the universal and spiritual values of our people; finding one's place in society and developing on the basis of social relations; recognition of one's successes with spiritual satisfaction; preserving one's individuality based on spiritual values [7].

In conclusion, the spiritual values that are important in the educational activity of students are formed due to the intense pedagogical activity of the teacher. In order to develop the moral values of students, the teacher should constantly use the following tools in pedagogical activity:

the teacher considers the development of students' moral values specific to society as the basis of their pedagogical activity;

there are always opportunities for students to find effective solutions for mastering spiritual values thanks to the teacher's selfless work;

creation of necessary conditions by the teacher for students to study moral values regularly.

the teacher constantly teaches students to master universal moral values, increasing their motivation for reading.

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